

METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND METHOD VALIDATION FOR ESTIMATION OF LAMIVUDINE AND TENOFOVIR BY USING RP-HPLC METHOD

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Abstract: A simple, Accurate, precise method was developed for the simultaneous estimation of the Lamivudine and Tenofovir in Tablet dosage form. Chromatogram was run through Sun Fire C18 Column, 100Å, 10 µm, 4.6 mm X 250 mm, 1/pk Mobile phase containing Buffer 0.1%OPA: Acetonitrile taken in the ratio 60:40 was pumped through the column at the flow rate of 1 ml/min. Buffer used in this method was 0.1% OPA buffer. Temperature was maintained at 30°C. Optimized wavelength selected was 252 nm. Retention time of Lamivudine and Tenofovir were found to be 2.170 min and 3.059 min. %RSD of the Lamivudine and Tenofovir were and found to be 0.5 and 1.1 respectively. %Recovery was obtained as 100.30% and 100.18% for Lamivudine and Tenofovir respectively. LOD, LOQ values obtained from regression equations of Lamivudine and Tenofovir were 0.13, 0.40 µg/ml and 1.00, 3.40 µg/ml respectively. Regression equation of Lamivudine is $y = 9345.1x + 4104.8$, and $y = 8482.8x + 4786.6$ of Tenofovir. Retention times has been decreased and that run time was decreased, so that the method developed was simple and economical that can be adopted in regular way.

Keywords: Lamivudine, Method Development, Method Validation, Tenofovir, RP-HPLC

1. INTRODUCTION⁽¹⁻¹⁰⁾

HPLC : Component separation in a liquid combination is accomplished by the use of High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC). A stationary phase, or column filled with a separation medium, is passed through a stream of solvent (mobile phase) that has a liquid sample injected into it.

1.4 Method Development procedure

The development of high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) methods appears to involve a complex range of equipment, columns, eluent, and operation preparations. The following steps are typically followed in the process, which is dependent on the type of analytes.

Steps:

Step 1 - Selection of the Suitable HPLC method and the initial system

Step 2 - Selection of initial conditions

Step 3 - Selectivity optimization

Step 4 - System optimization

Step 5 - Method validation.

1.5 Stability Indicating Method

When measuring active ingredients, a stability-indicating assay method should be able to do so without being influenced by degradation products, process impurities, excipients, or other possible contaminants. When an industry employs an analytical procedure for release testing that indicates non-stability, it should be supplemented by another analytical procedure that can monitor impurities, including degradation products, both qualitatively and quantitatively. Stability-indicating analytical techniques should be used for assay stability investigations. Stability testing allows for the establishment of a retest period for the active ingredient or a pharmaceutical product's shelf life, as well as the recommendation of storage conditions.

1.6 Analytical method validation

System suitability, linearity, precision, accuracy, specificity, robustness, limit of detection, limit of quantification, and stability of samples, reagents, and instruments are all included in the method validation study.

2 DRUG PROFILE⁽¹⁰⁻¹⁵⁾

2.1 Lamivudine

Fig 2.1: Lamivudine structure

An analog of zalcitabine and a reverse transcriptase inhibitor where the pentose ring's 3' carbon is swapped out for a sulfur atom. Hepatitis B (HBV) and Human Immunodeficiency Virus Type 1 (HIV-1) are treated with it.

2.2 Tenofovir

Fig 2.2 Tenofovir structure

An HIV-1 integrase inhibitor called tenofovir prevents the viral genome from integrating into the host cell by blocking the strand transfer step (INSTI). This medication has minimal toxicity and excellent tolerability because its effect is not recognizable in human host cells.

3 MATERIAL AND METHODS⁽¹⁵⁻¹⁸⁾

3.1 Materials

- Aurobindo Pharma Ltd. provided pure medications (API) containing Tenofovir and Lamivudine
- Tenofovir (Tenolam) and Lamivudine in combination.
- Distilled water, Acetonitrile (C₂H₃N), Phosphate buffer, Methanol (CH₃OH), Potassium dihydrogen ortho phosphate buffer and the Ortho-phosphoric acid. All the above Mentioned chemicals and solvents are from the Rankem.

3.2 Methods⁽¹⁸⁾

Diluent: Based up on the solubility of the drugs, diluent was selected, Acetonitrile and Water taken in the ratio of 50:50

Preparation of buffer :

Buffer: (0.1% Ortho-phosphoric acid)

In a 1000 ml volumetric flask, add 1 ml of Ortho phosphoric acid solution. Then, add roughly 100 ml of milli-Q water to bring the total volume up to 1000 ml with milli-Q water.

Preparation of standard stock solutions: Reliability 30 mg of lamivudine and 30 mg of tenofovir working standards were weighed and transferred into a 100 ml clean dry volumetric flask. A 3/4th volume of diluent was then added, and the mixture was sonicated for five minutes before diluents were added to make up the remaining volume. (Tenofovir 300 ppm and Lamivudine 300 ppm)

Preparation of standard working solutions (100% solutions): One milliliter of each of the two stock solutions mentioned above was added to a ten milliliter volumetric flask. (30 ppm Tenofovir and 30 ppm Lamivudine)

Preparation of sample stock solutions : After calculating the average weight of five tablets, the weight of one tablet was transferred to a 500 ml volumetric flask. Five milliliters of diluent were then added, and the mixture was sonicated for twenty-five minutes. The volume was then made up with diluent and filtered using HPLC filters (600 µg/ml of Tenofovir and 600 µg/ml of Lamivudine).

Preparation of sampling working solutions (100% solutions): One milliliter of the filtered sample stock solution was added to a ten milliliter volumetric flask and dilute with it. (30 µg/ml of Tenofovir and 30 µg/ml of Lamivudine).

4. LITERATURE REVIEW

K. Vasantha et al., IJPSR (2022), Volume 13, Issue 9⁽¹³⁾ Doravirine, Lamivudine, and Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate they belong to the class of anti-viral drugs and they have been mostly used in the treatment of HIV-I infection. Here A combination of buffer (0.1% OPA) and Acetonitrile used as mobile phase has optimized the method for efficient separation of the drugs. Doravirine, Lamivudine and Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate has been eluted at the 2.431, 3.187min, and 4.338, respectively, with the good resolution. Here the linear regression coefficient for the

Doravirine, Lamivudine and Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate drugs was 0.999 across the concentration range of 12.5-75 µg/mL (Doravirine), 37.5-225 µg/mL (Lamivudine and Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate respectively).

Omobolanle Ayoyinka Omoteso et al.,⁽¹⁴⁾ (2022) Here An effective analytical method is mainly requisite to ensure that the accurate identification, quantification of drug(s), Here either in the bulk material or in complex matrices, which any form part of finished pharmaceutical products. The suitable method has been developed by using a Kinetex® C18, 250 × 4.6 mm column as the stationary phase and as the mobile phase consisting of 50 : 50 v/v methanol and the water with 1 mL orthophosphoric acid, with a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min and column temperature maintained at 35°C. Here detection wavelength of 260 nm and the injection volume which consists of 10 µL were used. Here the Acceptable correlation coefficients for linearity (R²) of >0.998 for the each of the three drugs were obtained And the LOD had been quantified to be 56.31 µg/mL, 40.27 µg/mL, and 7.00 µg/mL for 3TC, TDF, and DTG, respectively and Here the LOQ was quantified as 187.69 µg/mL, 134.22 µg/mL, and 22.5 µg/mL for 3TC, TDF, and DTG, respectively.

Gampa Nagamalleswari et al., vol. 14 No. 3 (2023)⁽⁹⁾ Objective: Here A Modest, accurate and the specific Ultra Performance Liquid Chromatography which stability indicating method has been technologically advanced for the simultaneous estimation of the drugs Lamivudine, Tenofovir, and Dolutegravir in substance and in tablet dosage form. A chromatographic behaviour has been given with Acetonitrile and 0.1% formic acid in the ratio of 80:20 as mobile phase, waters X-Bridge C8100mm x 3.0mm, 3.5µm with a flow rate of the 0.5 ml/min and monitored at the 252 nm.

Results: Here the mean retention time of the drugs Lamivudine, Tenofovir, and Dolutegravir were found to be 0.879, 1.571 and 0.607 min respectively. And Linearity of Lamivudine, Tenofovir, and Dolutegravir was found to be 20-120 µg/mL, 20-120 µg/mL and 3.4 -20.4 µg/ml respectively.

Swapna Vemireddy et al.,⁽⁸⁾Vol. 30 No.8 (2023) Here the present study which provides us the single analytical tool for the main determination of the drugs elvitegravir, cobicistat, emtricitabine and tenofovir disoproxil fumarate in dosage forms. Here For this method normally an Agilent with 1200 is used, and High performance liquid chromatography system and the Acquity Ethylene Bridged Hybrid technology (BEH) C18, 1.7µ. 100 x 2.1 mm column these are used. Here the gradient program has been adjusted at the 0.3 ml/min flow rate and with 10 µl injection volumes were maintained here. Detection wavelength of 260 nm is found to be specific and it could able to provide precise area counts for the 3 each drug. Calibration curves has been depicting a proper linearity response from the concentration versus area observed for the each drug with the correlation coefficients of greater than 0.99. And The eluted compounds were monitored at the 240 nm.

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION⁽¹⁸⁻²⁵⁾

5.1 Method development: Method development was completed by changing the various, mobile phase ratios, buffers etc.

Optimized method:

Chromatographic conditions:

Mobile phase	:	60% 0.1% OPA : 35% Acetonitrile
Flow rate	:	1 ml/min
Column	:	SunFire C18 Column, 100Å, 10 µm, 4.6 mm X 250 mm, 1/pk
Detector wave length	:	252nm
Column temperature	:	30°C
Injection volume	:	10µL
Run time	:	6min
Diluent	:	Water and Acetonitrile in the ratio 50:50
Results	:	Both peaks have the good resolution, tailing

Factor, theoretical plate count and the resolution

Fig 5.1: Optimized Chromatogram

Observation: Lamivudine and Tenofovir were eluted at the peak 2.170 min and 3.059 min respectively with the good resolution. Plate count and tailing factor was very satisfactory for both the peaks so this method was optimized and to be validated.

5.2 Assay: Montek Plus Tab, which bearing the label claim containing the Lamivudine 10mg + Tenofovir 10mg. Assay was performed and with the above formulation. Average % Assay for Lamivudine and the Tenofovir obtained was 99.87 and 99.77% respectively.

5.3 System suitability

All the system suitability parameters were present within the range and they are satisfactory as per ICH guidelines.

Fig 5.2: Optimized chromatogram

Discussion: Here According to ICH guidelines plate count was should be more than 2000, and tailing factor should be less than 2 and resolution must be more than 2. All the system suitable parameters here were passed and were within the limits.

5.4 Linearity⁽²⁵⁻²⁸⁾

Fig 5.3: Calibration curve of Lamivudine

Fig 5.4: Calibration curve of Tenofovir

Discussion: Six linear concentrations of the two the drugs Lamivudine (2.5-15 μ g/ml) and the Tenofovir (2.5-15 μ g/ml) were injected in a duplicate manner. Average areas result were has been mentioned in above and linearity equations were obtained for the two drugs Lamivudine was the $y = 21374x + 7937$ and of Tenofovir was $y = 23897x + 14256$ Correlation coefficient obtained was the 0.999 for the two drugs.

5.5 Precision

5.5.1 System Precision

Discussion: From a single volumetric flask of the working standard solution six injections were has given and the obtained result areas were mentioned above. Average area, standard deviation and % RSD was calculated for the two drugs. % RSD obtained was the 0.7% and 0.5% respectively for the Lamivudine and Tenofovir. As the limit of the Precision was given has less than “2” then here the system precision was passed in this method.

5.5.2 Repeatability⁽²⁸⁻³⁰⁾

Discussion: Multiple sampling from the sample stock solution was done and the six working sample solutions of same concentrations was prepared here, each injection from each working sample solution was given and obtained resulted areas were has mentioned in the above table. Average area, standard deviation and % RSD were calculated for two drugs and obtained result as 0.8% and 0.7% respectively for the both Lamivudine and Tenofovir. As normally the limit of the Precision was less than the “2” so the system precision was passed in this method.

5.5.3 Intermediate precision

Discussion: Multiple sampling from a sample stock solution has been done and six working sample solutions of same concentrations was prepared here, each injection from the each working sample solution was given on the next day of the sample preparation and obtained resulted areas were mentioned in the above table. Average area, standard deviation and % RSD were calculated for both two drugs and obtained as 0.8% and 0.7% respectively, for Lamivudine and Tenofovir. As normally the limit of Precision was given has less than “2” so the system precision was passed in this method.

5.6 Accuracy

Discussion: Three levels of the Accuracy samples were prepared here by the standard addition method. Triplicate injections were given for the each level of accuracy and mean % Recovery was obtained as 99.71% and 100.10% for the both drugs Lamivudine and Tenofovir respectively.

5.7 Robustness

Discussion: Robustness conditions like Flow minus (0.9ml/min), Flow plus (1.1ml/min) and for mobile phase minus (65B:35A) for mobile phase plus (55B:45A), temperature minus (25°C) and for temperature plus(35°C) was maintained and the samples were injected in a duplicate manner. Here System suitability parameters were not much affected here and all the parameters were passed. % RSD was within the given limit.

5.8 Degradation chromatograms⁽³⁰⁻³⁴⁾

Table 5.3: Degradation data

Type of degradation	Lamivudine		Tenofovir	
	% Recovered	% Degraded	% Recovered	% Degraded
Acid	95.41	4.59	93.94	6.06
Base	93.45	6.55	94.51	5.49
Peroxide	96.48	3.52	99.34	0.66
Thermal	97.92	2.08	98.08	1.92
Uv	99.32	0.68	98.37	1.63
Water	99.81	0.19	97.94	2.06

5.8.1 Acid degradation chromatogram

Fig 5.5: Acid degradation chromatogram

RESULT: In acid degradation chromatogram the results obtained with the peak Lamivudine with 2.162 and Tenofovir with 3.131.

5.8.2 Base degradation chromatogram

Fig 5.6: Base degradation chromatogram

RESULT: In base degradation chromatogram the results obtained with the peak Lamivudine with 2.149 and Tenofovir with 3.115.

5.8.3 Peroxide degradation chromatogram

Fig 5.7: Peroxide chromatogram

RESULT: In Peroxide degradation chromatogram the results obtained with the peak Lamivudine with 2.162 and Tenofovir with 3.131.

4.8.4 Thermal degradation chromatogram

Fig 5.8: Thermal degradation

RESULT: In Thermal degradation chromatogram the results obtained with the peak Lamivudine with 2.147 and Tenofovir with 3.101.

5.8.5 UV degradation chromatogram

Fig 5.9: UV degradation

RESULT: In Uv degradation chromatogram the results obtained with the peak Lamivudine with 2.148 and Tenofovir with 3.115.

5.8.6 Water degradation chromatogram

Fig 5.10: Water

RESULT: In Water degradation chromatogram the results obtained with the peak Lamivudine with 2.147 and Tenofovir 3.106.

6. SUMMARY & CONCLUSION**6.1 Summary Table**

Parameters		Lamivudine	Tenofovir	LIMIT
Linearity ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)		7.5-45 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	7.5-45 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	R < 1
Regression coefficient		0.999	0.999	
Slope in (m)		9345.1	8482.8	
Intercept(c)		4104.8	4786.6	
Regression equation ($Y=mx+c$)		$y = 9345.1x + 4104.8$	$y = 8482.8x + 4786.6$	
Assay Expressed has (% mean assay)		100.10%	99.62%	90-110%
Specificity of Lamivudine, Tenofovir.		Specific	Specific	Here no interference of any peak
System precision %RSD		0.5	1.1	NMT 2.0%
Method precision %RSD		0.5	0.6	NMT 2.0%
Accuracy %recovery		100.30%	100.18%	98-102%
LOD		0.13	1.00	NMT 3
LOQ		0.40	3.04	NMT 10
Robustness	FM	0.3	0.9	%RSD NMT 2.0
	FP	0.1	0.1	
	MM	1.4	0.9	
	MP	0.1	1.4	
	TM	1.4	0.7	
	TP	1.4	0.3	

6.2 Conclusion

A simple, Accurate, precise method was developed for the simultaneous estimation of the Lamivudine and Tenofovir in injection dosage form. Retention time of Lamivudine and Tenofovir were found to be 2.170 min and 3.059 min. %RSD of the Lamivudine and Tenofovir were and found to be 0.5 and 1.1 respectively. %Recovery was obtained as 100.30% and 100.18% for Lamivudine and Tenofovir respectively. LOD, LOQ values obtained from regression equations of Lamivudine and Tenofovir were 0.13, 0.40 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 1.00, 3.40 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ respectively. Regression equation of Lamivudine is $y = 9345.1x + 4104.8$, and $y = 8482.8x + 4786.6$ of Tenofovir. Here the Retention time was decreased so that the run time was also decreased, so the method developed was simple and economical that can be adopted in regular Quality control test in the Industries.

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